

EFFECT OF SiC PARTICULATE SIZE ON PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF SiCp/2024Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The 2024Al aluminum alloys reinforced by 15vol.%SiC particulates of 3.5, 10 and 20 μm in size were fabricated by powder metallurgy technique. Tensile tests indicate that the strength of the composites decreases with increasing SiC particulate size, whereas the elongation-to-failure increases. SiC particulate size has no effect on the elastic modulus and the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the composites. The tensile fracture processes were in-situ observed by SEM. It was indicated that the microcracks initiated in the matrix adjacent to SiC particulates in the SiCp(3.5 μm)/2024Al composite, and no SiC particulate cracked. For the SiCp(20 μm)/2024Al composite the microcracks initiated by SiC particulate cracking, and the fracture of the composite was caused by the cracking of a lot of SiC particulates.

Keywords: composite, SiC, aluminum alloy, property, fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum matrix composites reinforced by ceramic particulate reinforcement are of great interest to structural engineers due to their high specific strength and modulus [1-3]. Generally, the modulus, fracture toughness, strength and ductility of those composites are determined by the particulate size and the volume fraction, the flow stress of matrix and the interfacial bonding between particulate and matrix [3-5].

It was reported that the particulates in the composite cracked typically for those size above 15-20 μm [5,6] and the composite flow strength decreased with increasing particulate size [6,7]. Therefore, it is important to understand the effect of SiC particulate size on the properties and fracture behavior of the composites. In this investigation the tensile tests and in-situ observations were performed to illustrate this effect.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The atomized 2024Al (wt. %:4.20Cu-1.47Mg-0.56Mn-0.02Zr-0.40Fe-0.27Si) powders (-140 mesh)

were employed as the matrix alloy. α -SiC particulates with a mean size of 3.5, 10 and 20 μm were used as the reinforcements. The composites containing 15vol.%SiC particulates were fabricated by P/M technique which involved mixing SiC particulates with Al powders, hot compaction in vacuum, and then hot extrusion at an extrusion ratio of 20:1. The tensile specimens having a gauge diameter of 4 mm and a gauge length of 10 mm were machined from the extruded rods which were T6-treated, and then tested at a strain rate of $8.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$. The fracture surfaces were examined with SEM. The elastic moduli of the composites were measured on machined rods of 8 mm diameter and 180 mm length using a resonance technique. The coefficient of thermal expansion of the composites was measured. The abrasion tests were performed with a pin-on-disk machine using emery abrasive paper of 600 grit. The wear rate was defined as the reduction of specimen weight per unit sliding distance. Dynamic tensile specimens were prepared by electrical discharged machining, then mechanical polished. Dynamic tensile tests were carried out using a scanning electron microscope equipped with a tensile stand. The microprocesses of fracture were observed continuously.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 shows the effects of SiC particulate size on the tensile properties of SiCp/2024Al composites. The tensile and yield strength of the composites decreases with the increasing of SiC particulate size, whereas the elongation-to-failure is improved. In Fig.2 the abrasive wear rate of the composites and matrix alloy is plotted against load. The composites exhibit superior abrasive resistance over the unreinforced matrix alloy. The abrasive resistance increases obviously with the increment of SiC particulate size. The abrasive wear rate of the composites and the matrix alloy increases with increasing load, and the composite with large size of SiC particulates exhibits excellent abrasive resistance under high load. Table 1 and Table 2 give the elastic modulus and CTE of the composites. The SiC particulate size does not have obvious effect on the elastic modulus and CTE of the composites reinforced by 15vol.%SiC particulates. The elastic modulus of the composites increases by about 45% over that of the matrix alloy, whereas the CTE decreases by 40%.

Table 1 Elastic modulus of SiCp/2024Al composites

Particulate size	R.T.	100°C	200°C	300°C	350°C
3.5 μm	103.2	101.3	97.4	91.7	88.7
20 μm	99.9	97.7	93.7	91.1	89.9

Table 2. CTE of SiCp/2024Al composites (10^{-6})

Particulate size	R.T.-100°C	R.T.-200°C	R.T.-300°C	R.T.-400°C
3.5 μm	15.4	15.9	16.7	17.6
20 μm	15.4	16.0	16.9	17.8

The mechanical and physical properties of the composites change with varying the contents of SiC particulates or whiskers [8,9], i.e. the properties of the composites can be tailor-made by adjusting the content of SiC reinforcement. From the above results it can be seen that the mechanical properties of the composites can be varied by altering the SiC particulate size without the variation of the physical properties. The desired mechanical and physical properties can be conveniently tailor-made by adjusting the content and/or the size of SiC particulates, which is significant for practical applications of the composites. It is noted that the strength of

the composites containing 15vol%SiC particulates decreases a little with increasing SiC particulate size from 3.5 μm to 10 μm , whereas the elongation-to-failure of the composites is improved considerably. The SiC particulates of 10 μm should be preferentially chosen from the viewpoint of comprehensive properties.

The tensile fracture surfaces of the composites containing different size of SiC particulates were observed by SEM. There were obvious differences in the morphologies of the fracture surfaces. The fracture surfaces of the composite containing SiC particulates of 3.5 μm exhibited typical dimple morphologies, the edges between dimples were small and the plastic deformation was localized. There was no cracked particulate in the fracture surface and the pull-out particulates were few. When the size of SiC particulate was 10 μm , there were both the cracked particulates and large dimples caused by the pull-out particulates on the fracture surface, and the plastic deformation increased. For the composite reinforced by SiC particulate of 20 μm , the cracked particulates were exposed on the fracture surfaces and the plastic deformation of the matrix between the SiC particulates increased significantly.

The SEM photographs of tensile fracture processes of the composites containing SiC particulates of 20 μm are shown in Fig.4. The particulates were cracked under low stress (Fig.4a), and the cracks were widened and more particulates were cracked with increasing stress (Fig.4b,c,d). The cracking of a lot of SiC particulates resulted in the fracture of the composite (Fig.5a). For the composite containing SiC particulate of 3.5 μm , the microcracks initiated in the matrix adjacent to SiC particulates, the cracks propagated in the matrix by bypassing particulates or pulling-out of the particulates and there was almost no fractured particulate (Fig.5b).

SiC particulate is a polycrystal, the probability of defects in the particulate increases and the strength of the particulate decreases with increasing the size of SiC particulate. On the other hand, the SiC particulates with large size usually have an aspect ratio of greater than one and are aligned along the extrusion direction after extrusion. The increase in size of SiC particulate makes the stress transferred to SiC particulate increase significantly since interfacial shearing. These factors result in the crack of large SiC particulates under low stress. It was reported [5,6] that the SiC particulates with the size of above 15-20 μm were typically cracked when the composite was loaded. For the composite reinforced by SiC particulates of 3.5 μm , the stress transferred to SiC particulates was low due to the small particulate size, and the strengthening mechanism in the composite was basically attributed to the particulate-dislocation interaction by means of the Orowan bowing mechanism [10]. The particulate cracking almost did not occur because SiC particulates were loaded by low stress. The cracking usually occurred in the matrix adjacent to SiC particulates due to excellent interfacial bonding between SiC and matrix, and the fine dimples were caused by the pull-out of SiC particulates covered with a coating of aluminum matrix. The high strength of the composite containing small particulates is mainly caused by Orowan strengthening mechanism. The fineness and dispersion distribution of SiC particulates have intense inhibition on the plastic deformation of the matrix, so the plastic deformation in the composite is localized and the ductility is low. The main strengthening mechanism of the composite reinforced by SiC particulates of 20 μm is particulate load-bearing through interfacial shearing due to the increase in interparticle distance and the Orowan mechanism is not dominant. The composite exhibits low strength is due to the particulate cracking under low stress. The reduction in the particulate inhibition of plastic deformation of the matrix due to the increase of interparticle distance and the relaxation in stress of the matrix caused by particulate cracking make the plastic deformation of the matrix develop fully, and the ductility of the composite is significantly improved. When SiC particulates are of 10 μm , both Orowan mechanism and particulate load-bearing mechanism contribute to composite

strengthening. Small particulates are pull out and large particulates cracked, so the composite has the moderate strength and ductility.

4. CONCLUSION

1. The strength of the SiCp/2024Al composite decreases with the increasing size of SiC particulates from 3.5 μm to 20 μm , whereas the ductility and the abrasive resistance are improved significantly.
2. The size of SiC particulates basically has no effect on the elastic modulus and the CTE of the composites containing 15vol.%SiC particulates.
3. Increasing the SiC particulate size from 3.5 μm to 20 μm the fracture model of the composites changes from the cracking of matrix adjacent to SiC particulates to the particulate cracking, the features of the fracture surface change from dimples to cracked particulates. For the composite reinforced by SiC particulates of 10 μm the fracture model and the morphologies of the fracture surfaces exhibit mixed characteristics.

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Figure 1. Effect of SiC particulate size on tensile properties of the composites

Figure 2. Dependence of abrasive wear rate on the applied loads for the composites

Figure 3. Tensile fracture surface of the composites a. 3.5 μm b. 10 μm c. 20 μm

Figure 4. Tensile fracture processes of the composite containing SiC particulates of 20 μm

Figure 5. Crack propagation in the composites a. 20 μm b. 3.5 μm